

Original Research

Pseudomonas stutzeri AK17 Mediated Modulation of Plant Defence Responses under Drought Stress

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Abstract

Drought is one of the severe abiotic stresses that limits the growth and yield of crops, mainly in arid and semi-arid regions. Cluster bean (*Cyamopsis tetragonoloba* L.) is relatively tolerant but suffers physiological and biochemical detriments during prolonged water scarcity. Plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria provide a sustainable biological strategy for improving plant resilience under drought stress. This study demonstrates the potential of *P. stutzeri* AK17 in mitigating drought stress, which is currently underexplored. Greenhouse experiments were conducted to study the effect of drought on treated and untreated plants by withholding water for 4, 8 and 12 days. Various parameters such as osmolyte production, antioxidant enzyme activities (APX, SOD, CAT) and expression of drought-responsive genes (P5CS, BADH and CAT) in cluster bean were studied. It has been observed that *P. stutzeri* AK17 inoculation significantly enhanced the osmolyte accumulation under drought stress as compared to uninoculated plants. Decrease in the antioxidant enzyme activities in the *P. stutzeri* AK17-treated plants under severe stress suggests an efficient ROS homeostasis. Gene expression study revealed an upregulation of P5CS and BADH gene, while downregulation of the CAT gene on the 12th day of drought stress, which is correlated with the biochemical results. These findings indicate that there is some crosstalk between various defence mechanisms, and *P. stutzeri* AK17 has an important role in enhancing the defence systems. Therefore, the present work demonstrates the potential of *P. stutzeri* AK17 as a bioinoculant for enhancing drought tolerance in cluster bean under controlled greenhouse conditions, and future studies are required to evaluate its performance under field conditions for broader agricultural applicability.

Keywords

Drought stress, Cluster bean, *Pseudomonas stutzeri*, osmolytes, antioxidant enzymes, gene expression

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Citation: Jain, R., Saraf, M., Acharya, D., Shukla, R., Vyas, T., Modi, S., Panchal, T. (2026). *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17 Mediated Modulation of Plant Defence Responses under Drought Stress. *Acta Biologica Slovenica* 69 (2)

Received: 07.11.2025 / **Accepted:** 23.03.2026 / **Published:** 26.03.2026

<https://doi.org/10.14720/abs.69.2.24537>

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Modulacija obrambnih odzivov rastlin pod vplivom suše, ki jo povzroča *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17

Izvleček

Suša je eden izmed abiotičnih stresov, ki omejuje rast in pridelek poljščin, predvsem v sušnih in plosušnih regijah. Grozdasti fižol (*Cyamopsis tetragonoloba* L.) je relativno odporna rastlina, vendar pri daljšem pomanjkanju vode utrpri fiziološke in biokemične posledice. Rizobakterije, ki spodbujajo rast rastlin, zagotavljajo trajnostno biološko strategijo za izboljšanje odpornosti rastlin v sušnih razmerah. Naša študija predstavlja potencial *P. stutzeri* AK17 pri blaženju sušnega stresa, ki je trenutno premalo raziskan. V kontroliranem poskusu v rastlinjaku smo testirali učinek suše na obdelane in neobdelane rastline z zadrževanjem vode za 4, 8 in 12 dni. Proučevali smo različne parametre, kot so proizvodnja osmolita, aktivnost antioksidativnih encimov (APX, SOD, CAT) in ekspresija genov, ki se odzivajo na sušo (P5CS, BADH in CAT). Ugotovljeno je bilo, da je inokulacija s *P. stutzeri* AK17 ob suši znatno povečala kopičenje osmolita v primerjavi z neinokuliranimi rastlinami. Zmanjšanje aktivnosti antioksidativnih encimov v rastlinah, obdelanih s *P. stutzeri* AK17, v pogojih hude suše kaže na učinkovito homeostazo ROS. Študija genetske ekspresije je pokazala povečano ekspresijo genov P5CS in BADH, medtem ko se je 12. dan sušnega stresa zmanjšala ekspresija gena CAT, kar je v skladu z biokemičnimi rezultati. Ti rezultati kažejo, da obstaja medsebojna povezanost med različnimi obrambnimi mehanizmi, pri čemer ima *P. stutzeri* AK17 pomembno vlogo pri krepitvi obrambnih sistemov rastline. Študija dokazuje potencial *P. stutzeri* AK17 kot bioinokulanta za povečanje sušne tolerance pri fižolu v nadzorovanih rastnih pogojih, pri čemer so potrebne nadaljnje študije za oceno njegove učinkovitosti v poljskih pogojih za širšo uporabo v kmetijstvu.

Ključne besede

sušni stres, grozdasti fižol, *Pseudomonas stutzeri*, osmoliti, antioksidativni encimi, genska ekspresija

Introduction

The most severe economic losses in agriculture are caused by drought stress, which restricts crop growth and yield, especially in arid and semi-arid regions. This type of abiotic stress affects the plant's water relationship at the cellular and systemic levels, leading to both specific and generalised reactions and damages (Chaffai et al., 2024). Basic physiological indicators involve diminished water content, lowered leaf water potential, loss of turgor, stomatal closure, and impaired cellular development and expansion. Acute water stress ultimately leads to plant mortality by inhibiting photosynthesis and altering metabolic processes (Qiao et al., 2024). Plants have many strategies to cope with drought, such as osmotic adjustment via producing compatible solutes (such as proline, glycine betaine, trehalose) and by expression of some stress-responsive genes (Chieb & Gachomo 2023). However, the inbuilt tolerance of many plants is limited, and an enhanced mechanism is needed to mitigate drought stress and sustain agricultural productivity under stress.

One promising approach to mitigate drought stress is the use of plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR). The interaction of these beneficial bacteria with plants manifests a variety of physiological, biochemical, and molecular activities (Nad et al. 2024). PGPR improves drought tolerance ability in plants through multiple, often synergistic mechanisms, such as producing phytohormones, improving nutrient uptake, production of exopolysaccharide (EPS), which helps to retain soil moisture and lowering stress-induced ethylene levels by ACC deaminase activities (Jain & Saraf, 2023). Moreover, inoculation with PGPR also results in increased osmolytes accumulation, decreased lipid peroxidation and ROS accumulation, and improved activities of antioxidant enzymes such as superoxide dismutase (SOD), catalase (CAT) and ascorbate peroxidase (APX) under drought stress (Al-Turki et al. 2023). A recent review shows that PGPR-induced drought tolerance consists of an integrated network of physiological, biochemical, and molecular modifications in host plants (Liu et al. 2025).

Among PGPR, *Pseudomonas* species have been studied extensively for their stress-ameliorating poten-

tial. Some recent studies show that *Pseudomonas* spp. play an important role in improving plant tolerance to abiotic stresses. For example, *Pseudomonas* ms22 possesses various plant growth-promoting activities which improve the growth of its host plant, i.e., sorghum under drought-mimicking conditions (Mulugeta et al. 2025). Inoculation of *Arabidopsis thaliana* with *Pseudomonas koreensis* S4T10 helps the plant cope with drought and salt stress (Kalleku et al. 2024). *Pseudomonas stutzeri* also shows promising results under abiotic stress such as salinity stress. For example, inoculation of *P. stutzeri* mitigates salt stress in lettuce, sunflower, barley and sorghum (Szymańska et al. 2022) and also heavy metal stress in *Lemna* species (Gulmez et al. 2023). These studies show that *P. stutzeri* possesses adapted stress-mitigating properties that extend beyond salinity, potentially into drought stress scenarios.

Cluster bean (also known as guar, *Cyamopsis tetragonoloba*) is a leguminous crop of economic importance in arid and semi-arid regions. It grows under conditions of water scarcity, which makes it a suitable source for drought mitigation studies. Only a few studies were reported on PGPR-induced drought tolerance in cluster bean, particularly with *Pseudomonas stutzeri*. Our previous research (Jain & Saraf, 2023) revealed *P. stutzeri* AK17 as a promising strain by screening for abiotic stress tolerance, plant growth-promoting characteristics, and pot trials.

In this study, we aim to examine the role of *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17 in augmenting drought tolerance in cluster bean in greenhouse conditions. We hypothesise that inoculation with *P. stutzeri* AK17 enhances drought tolerance in cluster bean by regulating physiological, biochemical and molecular defence mechanisms. Mainly, we propose that inoculation of AK17 (i) enhances osmolytes accumulation to maintain cellular osmotic balance (ii) reduces oxidative damage by regulating ROS levels and lipid peroxidation (iii) regulates key stress-responsive genes, including pyrroline-5-carboxylate synthase (P5CS), Betaine aldehyde dehydrogenase (BADH) and catalase (CAT) under drought stress. These hypotheses were tested through integrated physiological, biochemical and gene expression analyses.

Material and methods

On the basis of abiotic stress tolerance, plant growth-promoting traits and pot study from our previous study (Jain

& Saraf, 2023), *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17, which was isolated from the rhizosphere of cluster bean, was selected for this study.

Seed sterilisation and biopriming

Surface sterilisation of cluster bean seeds was done by treatment with 75% ethanol for 1 min, followed by dipping the seeds in 1% sodium hypochlorite (NaOCl) for 30 sec, and afterwards washing them properly with sterile distilled water 4 to 5 times. The soil used for the pot study was collected from Gujarat University, Ahmedabad, India. The soil was of loamy texture with a pH of 7.5, electrical conductivity 0.42 ds/m, organic carbon content 0.74%, available nitrogen 0.08%, available phosphorus 0.012 %, and available potassium is 0.015%. Prior to the pot study, the soil was sterilised by autoclaving at 15 psi at 121 °C for 20 min, 2 times at an interval of 24 h. The AK17 strain was inoculated in nutrient broth and incubated for 24h – 38h under shaking conditions at 100 rpm for activation. The activated broth was centrifuged at 8000 rpm for 10 min. The pellet was resuspended in sterile distilled water, and cell density was maintained at 10⁸ CFU/ml. The sterilised cluster bean seeds were allowed to soak in this bacterial suspension for 20 min and then allowed to air-dry. The seeds were then used for planting in pots; untreated seeds soaked in sterile distilled water were used as a control.

Experimental setup

The experiment was conducted in a completely randomised design with three replicates per treatment. Five seeds were planted per pot (8.0 cm × 11 cm size) filled with 2 kg sterile loam soil. The plant survival rate was recorded after 15 days of sowing. The cluster bean seeds were allowed to germinate and grow for 21 days under greenhouse conditions maintained at 28 ± 2 °C temperature, 60-70% relative humidity. Plants were irrigated at regular intervals for 21 days. After that, three levels of drought stress were given by withholding water for 4 days, 8 days and 12 days. Soil inoculation with bacterial suspension was done prior to the initiation of drought stress.

Leaf samples were collected at different time intervals, i.e., 0, 4, 8, 12 days of drought stress, to study various defence mechanisms developed by treated and untreated plants. Three plants were selected randomly from each treatment.

Proline content

The method described by Ahmed and Hassan (2011) was used to measure the proline content of leaves. Fresh leaves (0.5 g) from each treatment were collected and homogenised with 10 mL of 3% sulfosalicylic acid. The homogenised mixture was centrifuged for 5 min at 10,000 rpm. After centrifugation, 2 ml of the supernatant was collected in a fresh test tube and mixed with an equal amount of glacial acetic acid and freshly prepared ninhydrin reagent. This mixture was heated in a water bath at 90 °C for 1 h, and then the mixture was quickly transferred to ice to stop the reaction. 5 mL of toluene was added to the reaction mixture, followed by 15 sec of vortexing. The tubes were incubated for 20 min at room temperature in the dark to allow the toluene and aqueous phases to separate. The upper layer, containing the extracted proline, was collected in a separate test tube. Afterwards, the absorbance was measured at 520 nm using a spectrophotometer. The standard curve was prepared by using different concentrations of pure proline ranging from 0 to 100 µg/mL

Total amino acid content

The total amino acid content of the leaves was determined using the ninhydrin method. Freeze-dried leaf sample of 1000 mg was ground in 5 mL methanol-chloroform-water solution (60:25:15 v/v) and incubated at 60 °C for 2 h. The samples were then centrifuged at 10,000 rpm for 30 min. Total amino acid content was evaluated by heating 1 mL of the supernatant with 1 mL of 0.1M acetate buffer and 1 mL of 5% ninhydrin (in ethanol) at 95 °C for 15 min, and this was then finally cooled to room temperature. Absorbance was measured at 570 nm using a spectrophotometer. The amino acid leucine was used to prepare the standard curve (Starcher 2001).

Total soluble sugar content

Total soluble sugar content was calculated according to the method described by Dubois et al. (1951). Fresh leaves from all treatments were collected and ground with 3 mL of 80% methanol, followed by heating them in a water bath at 70 °C for 30 min. Then concentrated sulphuric acid H₂SO₄ (1.5 mL) was combined with an equal volume of extract (0.5 mL) and 5% phenol before being incubated again for 30 min in the dark. The absorbance of the sample was measured at

490 nm. Glucose was used to prepare a standard curve, and the sugar content was expressed as µg/g FW.

Glycine betaine content

Glycine betaine content was calculated using the spectrophotometer method described by Grieve and Grattan (1983). The collected leaves were shaken mechanically in deionised water at 25 °C for two days. Followed by filtration, the cell-free supernatant was diluted with 1.5 ml H₂SO₄ (2 N) sulfuric acid. Afterwards, it was allowed to cool down, and then 0.05 mL of cold KI-I₂ (potassium iodide-iodine reagent) was added to the mixture. A complex form after incubation was separated from the acid mixture by centrifugation. This complex in crystal form was dissolved in 1, 2-dichloro ethane (9 mL) and then incubated for 2 h. After incubation, the absorbance was analysed at 365 nm. Glycine betaine of Himedia was used to plot a standard curve, and the glycine betaine value was calculated as µg/g.

Lipid peroxidation

The amount of lipid peroxidation in cluster bean leaves was measured by the method described by Wu et al. (2014). The thiobarbituric acid test was used to measure the content of malondialdehyde (MDA) in the leaves. 0.5 g of fresh leaves were mixed with the 100 mM phosphate buffer to acquire a final volume of 8 mL. After centrifugation at 15,000 rpm for 20 min at 4 °C, the supernatant was collected. To this collected supernatant (1.5 ml), a reaction mixture (2.5 ml) containing 5% Trichloroacetic acid (TCA) and Thiobarbituric acid (TBA) was added. This solution mixture was incubated in a water bath at 100 °C for 30 min and then allowed to cool down at room temperature. After that, the mixture was centrifuged at 4800 rpm for 10 min, and the supernatant was collected in a fresh tube. Using a spectrophotometer, the absorbance of the supernatant was taken at 532 nm. The mixture of TCA and TBA was used as a blank for the spectrophotometer.

Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) content

The H₂O₂ content of the leaves was calculated by the method described by Velikova et al. (2000) with some modifications. The 0.25 g leaves were crushed in 5% TCA (3 ml) and 0.1 g activated charcoal at 0 °C. The mixture was centrifuged for 15 min at 12,000g. Take 0.5 ml of supernatant and

add an equal volume of 10mM potassium phosphate buffer and 0.75 ml potassium iodide (1M). The absorbance was measured by a UV-VIS spectrophotometer at 390 nm, and the H₂O₂ content was determined as µmol g⁻¹ DW.

Non-enzymatic mechanism: total phenol and total flavonoid content

The plant leaves were shade-dried at room temperature and finely powdered. The powdered material was extracted with 95% ethanol in 1:10 w/v by maceration for 48h at room temperature with intermittent shaking. The extraction was repeated three times to ensure complete recovery of bioactive compounds. The solvent was evaporated in the rotary evaporator, and the dried extract was obtained. About 10-50 mg of the dried extract was dissolved in methanol and used to calculate phenol and flavonoid content.

Total phenol content was studied using the method described by Wolfe et al. (2003). Folin-Ciocalteu reagent, which had previously been prepared as a 10% v/v dilution in distilled water, was combined with 0.5 ml of the leaf extract solution. The mixture turned blue after the addition of 4 mL of 75% anhydrous sodium carbonate. The resulting mixtures were vortexed and incubated at 40°C for 30 min. Afterwards, the absorbance was measured at 765nm using a UV-VIS spectrophotometer. Tannic acid was used to create the standard curve, and the sample's unknown content was estimated.

Utilising Ordonez's aluminium chloride technique, total flavonoid content was calculated (Ordonez et al. 2006). An equivalent volume of 2% aluminium chloride made using ethanol was mixed with 0.5 mL of the sample extract from the crushed leaves. After one hour of incubation at room temperature, the absorbance of the mixture at 420 nm was measured. A variety of quercetin concentrations were used for the calibration of the standard curve.

Enzymatic defence mechanism: superoxide dismutase, catalase, and ascorbate peroxidase

Plant leaves weighing 500 mg were crushed in the buffer containing 5 mL of a 50 mM phosphate buffer (pH 7.0) and 1% (v/v) polyvinylpyrrolidone (PVPP). The supernatant was obtained after centrifuging the crude extract at 10,000 g at 4 °C for 15 min, and this supernatant was used for antioxidant enzyme analysis.

The assay for superoxide dismutase, which relies on its capacity to prevent the photochemical reduction of nitro blue tetrazolium (NBT), was carried out using standard methodology (Ellouzi et al., 2013). The reaction mixture consists of 100 µl of the enzyme extract or the supernatant in 50 mM phosphate buffer, 75 µM NBT, 13 mM methionine, 2 µM riboflavin and EDTA (0.1 mM), making up the volume to 3 ml. This reaction mixture was incubated for 10 min at room temperature for the development of purple colour formazan. The absorbance was measured at 560 nm, and distilled water was used as a blank.

The catalase activity in the leaves of cluster bean was calculated according to the method described by Kumar et al. (2010). Equal parts of 300 mM H₂O₂ and H₂O were added to the enzyme extract (0.1 mL), along with 2.8 mL of 100% diluted 50 mM phosphate buffer. Catalase activity was calculated using the extinction coefficient of H₂O₂. One unit of catalase activity was defined as the amount of enzyme required to decompose 1 µmol of H₂O₂ per minute. The decrease in absorbance was measured at 240 nm.

The Starlin and Gopalakrishnan method (2010) was used to conduct the APX assay. 300 mM H₂O₂ (0.1 mL), 7.5 mM ascorbate (0.1 mL), 100% diluted 50 mM phosphate buffer (2.7 mL), and 1 mL of enzyme extract were added. In the reaction solution, distilled water was used as a blank in place of the enzyme solution. APX activity was calculated using the extinction coefficient of ascorbate (2.8 mM⁻¹ cm⁻¹). One unit of APX activity was defined as the amount of enzyme required to oxidise 1 µmol of ascorbate per minute. At a time interval of 0–60 seconds, the absorbance was measured at 290 nm.

Correlation analysis was performed to evaluate the relationships among enzymatic and non-enzymatic antioxidant parameters, including proline, total soluble sugar (TSS), glycine betaine (GB), phenol, flavonoid and malondialdehyde (MDA) content. Person correlations were

Expression of drought stress-responsive genes

Total RNA was extracted from young, fully expanded leaves of cluster bean plants. After harvesting, leaves were immediately frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at -80°C until further processing. RNA was extracted within 1 week of sample collection to ensure RNA integrity. All equipment, such as the mortar, pestle, glassware, spatula,

and other necessary items, was heated at 180°C for 5–6 hours. DEPC-treated sterile Milli-Q was used to treat the gel electrophoresis assembly and other plastic products. As per the requirement, the reagent was prepared with DEPC water as well. Approximately 0.1 g of plant leaves from each treatment were collected under sterile conditions and crushed in a pre-chilled mortar pestle with liquid nitrogen to form a fine powder. Total RNA was extracted using the PureLink™ RNA Mini Kit as per instructions. The purified RNA was quickly placed on ice for quantification and then stored at -80 °C for long-term use.

Total RNA samples were used to prepare the first strand of cDNA by reverse transcription using Verso cDNA synthesis kit (Thermo Scientific) according to the manufacturer's instructions. The synthesised cDNA was diluted five times with deionised water before use for the gene expression study. The expression of a specific gene was determined by using gene-specific primers (Suppl. Mat. Table S1), and the analyses of expression level by RT-PCR throughout the experiments were maintained by the reference gene. The expression level of three genes was studied under no stress and drought stress, i.e., CAT, BADH and P5CS and one reference gene, actin (ACT7). The primers were designed using IDT primer Quest software from the sequence of respective genes downloaded from the National Centre for Biotechnology Information (NCBI). qRT-PCR was performed using 2X Brilliant III SYBR green QPCR (Agilent Technologies, United States) in triplicate. The comparative Ct approach was used to assess the relative expression of the target gene in relation to a housekeeping gene (actin) and the samples (Rao et al., 2013). The relative expression of the gene was analysed by using the $2^{-\Delta\Delta Ct}$ method (Livak and Schmittgen, 2001). By studying the melting curve, the dissociation curve analysis of each sample was done to verify the specificity of the reaction (Sah et al. 2014).

Statistical analysis

The result of all the experiments was expressed as mean \pm standard deviation of three replicates. The data were analysed using two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) to evaluate the effects of inoculation and drought stress duration and their interaction. When significant differences were observed ($p \leq 0.05$), Tukey's HSD test was applied for mean separation. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 24.0.

Results

Proline and amino acid content

An increase in the proline and amino acid content was observed with increasing drought stress in the *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17-treated plant, as well as in uninoculated control plants. However, accumulation was much higher in the treated plant under severe drought stress (Figure 1a, b). Treated plants show 1.3-fold and 1.7-fold higher accumulation of amino acid and 1.8-fold and 2.7-fold higher accumulation of proline as compared to control on the 8th and 12th day of drought stress, respectively.

Total soluble sugar (TSS) content

Total soluble sugar content of the treated and untreated plants was found to be increased under drought stress. Under the no stress condition, i.e., on 21st DAS, the *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17-treated plant shows 40% higher TSS as compared to the control. On the 4th, 8th and 12th day of drought stress, the AK17 inoculated plants showed 78%, 83% and 98% higher TSS content as compared to the uninoculated control, respectively (Figure 1c).

Glycine betaine content

The glycine betaine content of the control plants increased under drought stress, but at a very slow rate, while the *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17-treated plants showed an increase in the glycine betaine content till 12th day of drought stress and had higher accumulation of GB content. The AK17-treated plants showed an increase in the GB content by 1.5 fold, 2.3 fold and 3.0 fold on the 4th, 8th and 12th day of drought stress, respectively, compared to the control (Figure 1d).

Lipid peroxidation

The amount of lipid peroxidation of the cells due to drought stress was measured by calculating the malondialdehyde (MDA) content in plants. MDA levels increased during lipid peroxidation of plant cell membranes if plants were under drought stress. No significant difference was observed in the MDA content of control and treated plants in the absence of drought stress, but under drought stress, a significant difference was found between the treated

Figure 1. Analysis of a) Proline content, b) total amino acid content, c) Total soluble sugar content, and d) Glycine betaine content of treated and untreated plants on different days of drought stress.

Slika 1. Analiza a) vsebnosti prolina, b) skupne vsebnosti aminokislin, c) skupne vsebnosti topnih sladkorjev in d) vsebnosti glicinbetaina pri obdelanih in neobdelanih rastlinah na različnih dneh sušnega stresa.

and untreated plants. The inoculation with *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17 reduces the MDA level by 61% and 76.9% at the 8th and 12th day of drought stress, respectively, as compared to uninoculated control plants (Figure 2: a).

Hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) content

The production of H₂O₂ increased with an increase in drought stress in the treated and untreated plants. However, the plant treated with *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17 shows less increase in the H₂O₂ content than the untreated plant under drought stress. The AK17-treated plants show 1.2 fold, 1.85 fold and 1.7 fold decreases in the H₂O₂ content at 4th, 8th and 12th day of drought stress as compared to control (Figure 2: b).

Total phenol and flavonoid content

An increase in the phenol and flavonoid content of the treated and untreated plant leaves was observed under drought stress. The *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17-treated plants show 2-fold and 2.1-fold increases in the phenol and flavonoid content of the plant at the 12th day of drought stress compared to the control (Figure 3: a, b).

Enzymatic mechanism

Under well-watered conditions, not much difference was observed in the inoculated and uninoculated plants. On the 4th day of drought stress, the *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17-treated plant shows the highest SOD activity, and

Figure 2. Analysis of a) MDA content and b) H₂O₂ content of treated and untreated plants at different days of drought stress.

Slika 2. Analiza a) vsebnosti MDA in b) vsebnosti H₂O₂ pri obdelanih in neobdelanih rastlinah v različnih dneh sušnega stresa.

Figure 3. Analysis of a) Total phenol content (TPC) and b) Total flavonoid content (TFC) of treated and untreated plants at different days of drought stress.

Slika 3. Analiza a) skupne vsebnosti fenolov (TPC) in b) skupne vsebnosti flavonoidov (TFC) pri obdelanih in neobdelanih rastlinah v različnih dneh sušnega stresa.

then the activity was decreased with an increase in drought stress as compared to the untreated control plant. The AK17-treated plant shows 36.6 % lower SOD activity compared to the control at the 12th day of drought stress. The antioxidant activity of the CAT and APX were also studied, which shows that the *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17-treated plants have an increase in the activity of both the enzymes with an increase in drought stress, but the increase in activity was significantly lower as compared to that of the untreated control plants (Figure 4: a, b, c). This decrease in the antioxidant enzyme activity in the *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17-treated plant suggests that inoculation with AK17 results in minimising the ROS production in the plant, thus helpful in mitigating the effect of drought stress.

Relationship between the various defence systems

A correlation between the various types of enzymatic and non-enzymatic defence mechanisms was studied. The correlation revealed a near-perfect correlation between the glycine betaine, phenol and flavonoid content. Also, there was a strong correlation between the proline, amino acid and total soluble sugar (TSS) content. A negative correlation was found in the MDA and proline, TSS, GB, phenol, and flavonoid content. This suggests that as the production of osmolytes and antioxidant compounds increased, the MDA content decreased, leading to a reduction in the lipid peroxidation of the cells under drought stress (Figure 5).

Figure 4. Analysis of the enzymatic activity of a) SOD, b) APX, and c) CAT of treated and untreated plants at different days of drought stress.

Slika 4. Analiza encimske aktivnosti a) SOD, b) APX in c) CAT pri obdelanih in neobdelanih rastlinah v različnih dneh sušnega stresa.

Figure 5. Relationship between the studied parameters ($p \leq 0.05$): MDA malondialdehyde, TSS total soluble sugar, APX Ascorbate peroxidase, GB glycine betaine, H₂O₂ hydrogen peroxide, SOD superoxide dismutase, and CAT catalase.

Slika 5. Razmerje med preučevanimi parametri ($p \leq 0,05$): MDA (malondialdehid), TSS (skupni topni sladkorji), APX (askorbat peroksidaza), GB (glicin betain), H₂O₂ (vodikov peroksid), SOD (superoksid dismutaza) in CAT (katalaza).

AK17 inoculation alters stress-related gene expression

In order to confirm the result of the biochemical analyses, qRT-PCR analysis of three stress-responsive genes, namely, pyrroline-5-carboxylate synthase (P5CS), betaine aldehyde dehydrogenase (BADH) and catalase (CAT) genes, was carried out in *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17-treated plants and untreated plants at different levels of drought stress. The relative expression of the gene on the 0th, 4th, 8th and 12th day of drought stress was studied.

The result shows the significant differential expression of the genes at various levels of drought stress, and the expression data are shown to be correlated with our biochemical results. Under no stress conditions, the AK17-

treated plant shows 2.7-fold upregulation in the P5CS expression compared to the untreated plant. Under the drought stress conditions, a gradual increase in the expression of the P5CS gene was observed in the inoculated and uninoculated plants. The maximum expression was found in the *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17 inoculated plant at the 12th day of drought and was 4.2-fold higher compared to the uninoculated control at that level of drought stress (Figure 6a). A similar pattern of expression was found for the BADH gene. Under no stress conditions, the gene expression in the treated plants was 1.7-fold higher compared to the untreated plants. An increase in the expression of the gene was observed in both the plants with an increase in drought level, but the upregulation of the gene was much higher in the treated plant compared to the untreated one. There was

a 5.3-fold higher expression of the BADH gene in the *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17 inoculated plant at the 12th day of drought compared to the uninoculated control (Figure 6b).

A different pattern of expression was found in the catalase (CAT) gene under drought stress. There was no significant difference in the expression pattern of the CAT gene in treated and untreated plants under non-stress conditions. But the expression of the CAT gene was changed at various levels of drought stress. A gradual increase in the gene expression with an increase in drought stress was observed in the uninoculated control plant, but in the inoculated plant, the expression of the gene was up-regulated till 4th day of drought stress, and then a gradual decrease in the expression of the gene was observed. The *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17-treated plant shows 3-fold higher gene expression on the 4th day of drought stress compared to the control, and then the gene was down-regulated till the 12th day of drought stress by 2.1-fold

Discussion

The results from the present study explained that inoculation of *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17 significantly improved drought-associated physiological and biochemical parameters such as osmolytes accumulation, ROS management, antioxidant defence mechanism and expression of some stress-responsive genes compared to uninoculated plants ($p \leq 0.05$). These findings support and deepen the present understanding of how the PGPR promotes growth in cluster bean plants under drought stress.

The current study shows the higher accumulation of proline, soluble sugar, amino acid and glycine betaine in AK17-treated plants, especially under severe drought stress (i.e., 8th and 12th day of stress). Chandra et al. (2018) observed an increase in the proline content in the wheat plant by 1.53 and 1.75-fold when treated with *Pseudomonas palleroniana* strain DPB16 and *Pseudomonas fluorescens* strain DPB15, respectively, under drought stress for 5 days. Similarly, Kour et al. (2020) found an increase in the proline content of wheat by 2-fold at 75% water regime when treated with *Pseudomonas libanensis* EU-LWNA-33. Proline is also important for maintaining the nitrogen content of cells and guards against dehydration-induced protein misfolding (Ghosh et al. 2017). Another strategy for preparing for osmotic adjustment during drought stress is the accumulation of soluble sugar as osmolytes (Mishra et

al. 2016). Batool et al. (2020) found an increase in the TSS content of the potato plant by 59% and 75% under moderate and severe drought stress conditions, respectively, when treated with PGPR as compared to the untreated control. An increase in the GB content by 1.2-fold was observed in the wheat plant at 75% water regime when treated with *Pseudomonas libanensis* EU-LWNA-33 (Kour et al. 2020). Some studies show that the accumulation of glycine betaine and soluble sugar serves as a reliable biochemical marker of PGPR-mediated drought tolerance (Gowtham et al., 2022). In the present study, we observed an increase in the accumulation of proline, soluble sugar and glycine betaine during severe drought stress (8th and 12th day), which suggests that AK17 inoculation induces a prolonged osmotic adjustment response, which may result from a better root water uptake system or bacterial signaling for osmolyte synthesis.

Drought stress results in the accumulation of reactive oxygen species (ROS) such as hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2), which cause damage to biomolecules such as lipid, protein and DNA. One way to measure lipid damage is by Malondialdehyde (MDA) content, which increases during drought in treated as well as in untreated plants, significantly higher in the latter. In the present study, inoculation of AK17 reduces the MDA content by 61% and 76.9% on the 8th and 12th day of drought stress, respectively, as compared to the untreated one. This shows that the AK17 treatment protects cell membrane integrity during severe drought. Mishra et al. (2016) found a significant decrease in the MDA content of the wheat on the 7th day of drought stress when treated with PGPR compared to the untreated control. In contrast to non-inoculated plants, PGPR inoculation reduced MDA buildup, which prevented membrane damage during drought. Chandra et al. (2018) found a decrease in the level of MDA at the 5th day of drought stress by 69.5% and 47.7% in the wheat plant inoculated with *Pseudomonas fluorescens* strain DPB15 and *P. palleroniana* strain DPB16, respectively. A significant decrease in the MDA content of the jujube (*Ziziphus jujuba*) under moderate and severe drought stress was observed when treated with *Pseudomonas lini* and *Serratia plymuthica* as compared to the untreated control plant (Zhang et al. 2020). The concentration of H_2O_2 also increases during drought stress, but the plant treated with AK17 has a lower level of H_2O_2 , which indicates that AK17 treatment results in scavenging or preventing the higher accumulation of ROS during drought stress. Similar results were observed by Batool et al. (2020), who found a

Figure 6. a) Semiquantitative RT-PCR analysis of P5CS transcript level in the leaves of cluster bean plant under drought stress; b) Semiquantitative RT-PCR analysis of BADH transcript level in the leaves of cluster bean plant under drought stress; c) Semiquantitative RT-PCR analysis of CAT transcript level in the leaves of cluster bean plant under drought stress.

Slika 6. a) Polkvantitativna analiza RT-PCR ravni transkripta P5CS v listih rastline fižola pod sušnim stresom; b) Polkvantitativna analiza RT-PCR ravni transkripta BADH v listih rastline fižola pod sušnim stresom; c) Polkvantitativna analiza RT-PCR ravni transkripta CAT v listih rastline fižola pod sušnim stresom.

significant decrease in the H_2O_2 content of the two varieties of potato under moderate and severe drought stress when treated with PGPR compared to the untreated control. So, together by lowering MDA content and H_2O_2 accumulation, the *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17 treatment develops an effective ROS detoxification system.

Antioxidant enzymes such as SOD, CAT, and APX play a very important role in detoxifying ROS along with non-enzymatic antioxidants such as phenols, flavonoids, etc. (Gowtham et al., 2022). The present study shows a significant increase in the phenol and flavonoid content in the AK17-treated plant compared to the control. While a complex pattern was observed for antioxidant enzyme activity, i.e., superoxide dismutase activity was higher at moderate drought stress (4th day) but decreased under severe stress. CAT and APX activity increase during drought stress, but it is lower in the AK17-treated plant as compared to the control. This pattern observed may be due to higher accumulation of osmolyte during severe drought

stress, due to which plants experience less accumulation of ROS to be detoxified by enzyme activity. A similar result was observed by Sandhya et al. (2010), which shows a lower antioxidant enzyme activity in the maize plant treated with various *Pseudomonas* spp. compared to the untreated control under drought stress conditions. Similarly, Tiwari et al (2016) found the reduction in the SOD and CAT enzyme activity in the chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.) plant treated with *Pseudomonas putida* under drought stress conditions as compared to the untreated control.

The study of gene expression is particularly significant as it links the biochemical observation with molecular regulation. In the present study, an upregulation of P5CS (involved in proline biosynthesis) and BADH (involved in glycine betaine biosynthesis) was observed in AK17-treated plants under drought stress. This is correlated with the higher accumulation of proline and glycine in the AK17-treated plant. Ghosh et al. (2017) observed an increase in the expression of the P5CS gene in the Arabidopsis

thaliana inoculated with *Pseudomonas putida* strain at 2 to 7 days of drought stress.

Upregulation was observed in CAT (involved in catalase synthesis) during the earlier drought stress period (4th day), but later during severe drought stress, its expression was downregulated in the treated plant as compared to the control. These results correlate with Tiwari et al. (2016) observation, where there was a 2.5-fold down-regulation in the expression of the CAT gene in chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.) plant treated with *Pseudomonas putida* under drought stress conditions, while the untreated control shows the up-regulation of this gene.

The observation in the present study shows that CAT is upregulated in the initial period of drought stress, but afterwards its expression decreases, which may suggest that *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17 enhances early responses, helps the plant to manage stress effectively, thus reducing the requirement of prolonged expression. This may reduce wastage of energy or prevent overactivation of antioxidant pathways, which can be expensive.

Conclusion

This study suggests that the inoculation of *Cyamopsis tetranogoloba* with *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17 helps in mitigating the various levels of drought stress by interacting with the physiological, biochemical and molecular mechanisms of the cluster bean plant. Inoculation with *Pseudomonas stutzeri* AK17 helped cluster bean to mitigate the osmotic stress at the advent of drought, which enabled it to grow and survive under severe drought stress. The expression

of three genes at different levels of drought stress corroborated our biochemical analysis. The ability of AK17 to enhance osmolytes accumulation, reduce ROS and membrane damage, activate the antioxidant defence system and regulate the expression of drought-responsive genes under controlled greenhouse conditions makes it a compelling option for bioinoculant development. This research also suggests that there was a crosstalk between different types of mechanisms adopted by the cluster bean plant to effectively mitigate the deleterious effects of drought. However, further studies under field conditions are required to confirm its effectiveness under natural agricultural conditions.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization, R.J. and M.S.; methodology, R.J.; investigation, R.J.; formal analysis, T.V., S.M. and T.P.; data curation, R.J.; writing-original draft preparation R.J.; writing-review and editing, M.S., D.A., and R.S.; supervision, M.S.; project administration, M.S. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding

This work was funded by the Department of Science and Technology (DST) New Delhi under Women Scientist (WOS-A) scheme (Sanction No. SR/WOS-A/ LS-194/2018).

Data Availability

Research data tables were deposited at Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19234513>).

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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